

Characterization of Geopolymer based Batteries Composites

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Abstract

In the recent years, geopolymer concrete is green technology of construction materials. Geopolymer concrete as a based battery composites with an innovative construction smart material for energy storage applications. The characterization of geopolymer-based battery by back carbon mixing with different of amount compositions. After mixing, the battery samples were carried out with all properties. The performance of the battery is based on the structural, morphological, electrical and electrochemical properties of the electrolytes. The results show that the properties of the battery are closely related to the percentage of chemicals composition.

Keywords: Geopolymers, composite materials, Cement Battery, Cement electrolyte, building materials and properties

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the urge of using geopolymer concrete as green construction materials has increased in infrastructure development besides increasing in awareness as a result of global warming (Abdullah et al., 2017). Geopolymer is supposed to be a new alternative material which the greenness of conventional concrete is improved likewise having a better performance compared to other concrete materials. Battery technology, particular solid-state batteries of an advanced building materials to provide multifunctional smart features such as self-powering (Borchers & Pieler, 2010). Due to the rising cost of fuel and the environmental pollution resulting from the burning of fuel, there is urgent need for energy such as generated by fuel cells, batteries, solar cells, thermoelectric devices, and wind mills. Among these sources of energy, batteries constitute the most developed source (Yin et al., 2024). However, their limited energy density makes conventional batteries unable to provide large amounts of energy (Zhang & Tang, 2021). Since then, advances have been in creating batteries with different electrode combustions for specific uses. Structurally, two metals or compounds of varying chemical potentials separated from each other by a separator constitute a battery (Sundaramoorthi & Thangaraj, 2023). Cement-based battery is a solid-state battery in which the pore water (solution) within the hardened cement paste is the primary electrolyte medium through which ion migration would occur. Hence, in the development of cement-based batteries, the main focus is on the enhancement of electrolytic (ionic) conduction property of the cement paste (Zhao et al., 2022). Providing exclusive generators and power lines at difficult-to-access locations way for the development of cement-based batteries, by which certain low-power operations shall be taken care of the building itself in a self-sustainable manner. With respect to corrosion protection, there are studies which have reported that a small current density applied intermittently could arrest the corrosion occurring in steel reinforcement. Some reports studied has mentioned to current density of 6 mA/m² was able to counter the corrosion rate of approximately 60 mA/m² in reinforced concrete system (Pickering, Efendy, & Le, 2016). Cathodic protection and cathodic

prevention are two kinds by which the steel reinforcements in concrete structure are protected from corrosion initiation and progression respectively (Kreislova & Geiplova, 2012). As far as cathodic protection is concerned, a recommended current density is around 5–20 mA/m² while for cathodic prevention a much lower current density of 1–2 mA/m². Therefore, the cement-based batteries can be projected for the application of cathodic prevention, a low-power operation that could operate at 1–2 mA/ m² (Zhang & Tang, 2021). In the present study, characterization of Geopolymer based Batteries Composites were investigated on their performance of the battery demonstrating the feasibility of developing rechargeable concrete battery with improved power output and energy capacity.

2. Material and Methodology

2.1. Materials

The raw material to use in this study a cement, fly ash, sand, MnO₂, Zince and Sodium hydroxide. The geopolymer battery is an electrolyte material as from the mixing of cement, fine sand with alkali solution of the Sodium hydroxide.

2.2. Battery preparation method

The battery preparation is made with two layers concrete specimens was produced by raw materials available in the national market were selected.

Figure. 1. Preparation process of geopolymer based battery

2.3. Battery testing method

2.3.1 Electrochemical teste

The electrochemical impedance spectrum of the geopolymer based battery electrolyte material was assessed using an electric meter to measure of the corrosion of steel reinforcement in concrete. This corrosion experiment uses an electrical grid to distribute reinforcement in concrete to determine the (anode) and (cathode) constants and change the concentration of a substance (NaCl) to accelerate corrosion and measure the electrical grid.

2.3.2. Charge and discharge test

The charge and discharge tests for rechargeable geopolymer cement-based battery were conducted using the lighting USB lam. For charge and discharge were applied about 6 to 8hrs according to (Yin et al., 2024).

3. Results and analysis

3.1. Electrochemical of cement-based battery

Figure 2 is the electrochemical of the geopolymer-based battery electrolyte sample shown below after preparing geopolymer based battery which was tested by the two-electrode method at the 7 days curing age (Abdullah et al., 2017; Bangera, Y, & Nazareth, 2024; Mahmoodi, Siad, Lachemi, Dadsetan, & Sahmaran, 2020; Sundaramoorthi & Thangaraj, 2023). The body conductivities of geopolymer based electrolyte is around 4.6 to 9.5V. From this result found that is lower when compare to other researchers (Zhang & Tang, 2021).

Figure.2. Overview of geopolymer based- battery sample for electrolyte ion conductivity teste.

3.2. Charging and discharging of battery

In this Figure 3 was displayed of the capacity of sample geopolymer cement-based battery during charging and discharging process. The volte in Figure 3 and current data course as Figure 4. Notably, we can see that the average discharge capacity of samples battery with concentrates adding material in the composition of sample.

Figure. 3. Details of geopolymer based battery samples (a) overview of charge (b) discharge and (c) contented geopolymer battery

Figure.4. Details of cyclic discharge capacity and efficiency of rechargeable cement-based battery

Following experimental research on over a hundred sample groups, a rechargeable cement-based battery with the highest performance to date was developed successfully, as well as its design parameters and preparation methods. As shown in Figure.4 before and after charging of samples capacity and efficiency of battery samples. Comparative analysis of Figure 4(a)-(b) before and after charging of battery to identify how long the electricity energy density of rechargeable.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we have focused on feasibility of geopolymer based battery concrete composite. The battery concrete composite was investigated on lighting in the samples after shaping in developing and characterizing a rechargeable cement-based battery for energy storage applications. Here some finding we have drawn: 1). the cement-based electrolyte displayed high ionic conductivity 2). Sample can be charge-discharge after using electricity into energy body.

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